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THE ROLE OF VERBAL FLUENCY ASSESSMENT IN PATIENTS WITH MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS

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Abstract

Introduction: Cognitive dysfunction can be a prominent feature in multiple sclerosis (MS) often manifesting itself as speech and language impairment and can have a devastating impact on psychosocial functioning. Neuropathologically, MS is associated with multiple focal areas of axonal demyelination; diffuse white matter pathology is believed to be particularly associated with executive dysfunction while verbal fluency measures have been shown to be a sensitive tool for detecting cognitive impairment.

Objective: The purpose of paper is to examine the presence and impairment rates of verbal fluency in patients with MS.

Materials and method: The research was conducted on a sample of 359 persons with two subsets of participants: a sample of persons with a relapsing-remitting form of MS ($n=108$) and a sample of persons from the general population ($n=251$). Audio-Recorded Cognitive Screen-ARCS was used as an instrument for detecting impairment in multiple cognitive domains such as memory, verbal fluency, language, visuospatial functions and attention.

Results: MS patients scored significantly worse on tests of verbal fluency ($M=31.02$ ($SD=8.02$)) in comparison to general population ($M=38.64$ ($SD=8.57$)). Deviations in all three categories of verbal fluency in patients with MS were found more prominent within the group of patients for whom time elapsed since diagnosis was longer than 10 years, older patients, as well as those with present cognitive impairment confirmed using ARCS ($F=21.58$, $p < 0.01$).

Conclusions: Test results showed deficiencies in both semantic and phonemic verbal fluency in patients suffering from MS where those who display more pronounced deficits tend to be older, have an increased duration of illness and greater cognitive impairment. Performance on fluency tests may be amongst the most sensitive measures of cognitive ability and could provide a simple mean to assess cognitive impairment so as to determine necessary preventive measures.

Key words: multiple sclerosis, verbal fluency, assessment, cognitive impairment

Introduction

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a chronic, inflammatory, demyelinating disease of the central nervous system (CNS) (Stadelmann, Wegner, & Brück, 2011). Neuropathologically, MS is associated with multiple focal areas of axonal demyelination and diffuse white matter pathology is believed to be particularly associated with executive dysfunction, which in turn results in clinical deficits and disability (Kutzelnigg & Lassmann, 2014). Neuropsychological changes in MS include both psychiatric disorders and cognitive deficits (Ben-Zacharia & Mathewson, 2017). Cognitive decline is recognized as a prevalent and debilitating symptom of MS including slowed information processing, impaired problem solving, reduced word-finding ability, decreased attention and concentration, memory loss, reduced visuospatial abilities, and reduced executive functioning (Sumowski, et al., 2018).

Prevalence estimates of cognitive impairment in MS range from 40% to 65%, depending on the research setting (Chiaravalloti & Deluca, 2008). Cognitive dysfunction encompasses all the disease stages and types of clinical course causing role limitations in work and social life, independently of the degree of physical disability. Conflicting literature data report that cognitive impairment could be considered an early feature of the disease or a consequence of its duration, course, and severity. Controlled studies, however, have clearly shown that cognitive deterioration tends to progress over time. Among clinical predictors, incipient cognitive decline seems to be the major risk factor for further deterioration in the short-term. In the long-term, the likelihood increases that also patients with initial cognitive preservation may deteriorate (Piras, 2003).

Tests of verbal fluency are amongst the most widely employed measures used to assess cognitive functioning following neurological damage (Paula, Paiva, & Costa, 2015). The tests are often included in the neuropsychological assessment, in clinical practice and in research. For instance, they have been used to support diagnosis of attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder – ADHD (Andreou & Trott, 2013), as well as of cognitive impairment in patients with neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's (Zhao et al., 2013) or Parkinson's disease (Pettit et al., 2013). The widespread use of the verbal fluency tasks probably stems in part from their face validity as tests of both verbal ability and executive control; they involve associative exploration and retrieval of words based on phonemic or semantic criteria (phonemic and semantic fluency, respectively), usually conducted in the setting of a time constraint. Whilst for phonemic fluency participants are asked to generate as many words as possible beginning with a specified letter (e.g. F), for semantic fluency search is constrained by a specified category (e.g. animals) (Shao, Janse, Visser, & Meyer, 2014). These measures are considered to impose comparable demands upon executive or supervisory processes because both require efficient organisation of verbal retrieval and recall, as well as self-monitoring aspects of cognition (the participant must keep track of responses already given), effortful self-initiation, and inhibition of responses when appropriate. Thus, serious deficits in either verbal ability or executive control should manifest themselves in poor performance in the fluency tasks. Therefore, both phonemic and semantic fluency tests are of interest as candidate screening tests (Connick, Kolappan, Bak, & Chandran, 2011).

The aim of this study is to examine the measures and the impairment rates of verbal fluency in patients with MS and, by utilizing verbal fluency assessment as a sensitive and ecologically valid tool for detecting cognitive impairment, promote the incorporation of cognitive assessment into MS clinics and clinical trials.

Materials and Methods

Participants

The sample consisted of 359 patients divided into two subsets: a sample of patients with a relapsing-remitting form of MS (pwMS, n=108) and a sample of persons from the general population (n=251). Descriptive characteristics of the participants are found in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive characteristics of the overall sample

	PwMS	General population
Age	M = 39.91, SD = 8.228, range 20 - 53	M = 35.24, SD = 12.84, range 18-65
Gender		
Male	38 (35.5%)	92 (36.7%)
Female	69 (64.5%)	159 (63.3%)
Education		
Elementary school	8 (7.47%)	8 (3.21%)
High school (3 years)	20 (18.69%)	23 (9.23%)
High school (4 years)	52 (48.59%)	82 (32.9%)
College degree	10 (9.34%)	20 (8.03%)
University degree	15 (14%)	76 (30.5%)
Specialization, Master's degree, Doctorate	1 (.93)	40 (16.06%)
Symptom onset time (years)	M = 14.23, SD = 6.88, range 4 - 34	
Time elapsed since the diagnosis of MS (years)	M = 10.74, SD = 5.19, range 4 - 29	

Eligibility criteria

Inclusion criteria:

- a confirmed diagnosis of MS according to the revised McDonald criteria 2005 (Polman et al., 2011)
- Relapsing-remitting type of multiple sclerosis (RRMS)
- Age between 18 and 55 years
- EDSS score 0-5.5 (Kurtzke, 1983)

Patients included in the research study were clinically stable (without exacerbations in the last 30 days) and the time elapsed since the diagnosis was longer than 6 months. The informed consent was obtained from all patients.

Exclusion criteria were: psychiatric disorders, history of substance abuse, brain injury or other conditions that could affect cognitive and motor abilities.

Ethical consideration

The study was approved by both the Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine and the Clinical Centre of Vojvodina.

Instruments

Instruments used for the assessment of cognitive deficits:

The Audio Recorded Cognitive Screen – ARCS (Schofield, et al., 2009) is a brief neuropsychological assessment specifically developed to detect cognitive impairments across a range of domains, while not being burdensome in terms of clinician time or resources. The ARCS is administered using a portable audio device (e.g. CD player, MP3) to patients who record their responses by writing in a specially designed response booklet that can later be scored. The battery consists of 8 subtests which measure abilities in 5 major domains: Memory, Verbal fluency, Language, Visuospatial abilities and Attention.

For the purposes of this research, we will further explain 4 out of 8 subtests of the ARCS relevant to this study.

Verbal fluency – Category - this subtest requires an elaborate retrieval of words from conceptual (semantic) memory. The subject is asked to produce as many names of items belonging to a certain category such as animals or fruit in a predefined timeframe (1 minute).

Verbal fluency – Activity - administered in the same way as the Category subtest, it requires a production of names regarding activities (verbs).

Verbal fluency – Letter - participants are asked to generate as many words as possible beginning with a specified letter in a predefined timeframe. In the original test the letter H was used due to its high frequency in the English language. The Serbian version of ARCS will be using the letter K on this test.

Language – Naming test - The subject is asked to write the names of the ten

displayed objects in the answer sheet. The result is the number of accurate responses of maximum 10 possible.

ARCS domain scores show good convergent validity with more comprehensive and established measures of cognitive performance.

Paced Auditory Serial Addition Test – PASAT – the test was developed to assess the effects of traumatic brain injury on cognitive functioning. Subsequent research has shown that the PASAT has clinical utility in detecting impairments in cognitive processing in patients with a wide variety of neuropsychological syndromes. The PASAT is a measure of cognitive function that assesses auditory information processing speed and flexibility, as well as calculation ability. Gronwall and Sampson (1974) originally assumed the PASAT measured speed of information processing. However, the PASAT is now recognized as a measure of multiple functional domains because it requires the successful completion of a variety of cognitive functions, primarily those related to attention.

The PASAT is presented using compact disk to ensure standardization in the rate of stimulus presentation. Single digits are presented every 3 seconds and the patient must add each new digit to the one immediately prior to it.

Instruments used for the assessment of neurological deficits:

The Expanded Disability Status Scale (EDSS) is a method of quantifying disability in multiple sclerosis and monitoring changes in the level of disability over time. It is widely used in clinical trials and in the assessment of people with MS. The EDSS scale ranges from 0 to 10 in 0.5 unit increments that represent higher levels of disability. Scoring is based on an examination by a neurologist. EDSS score 1.0 to 4.5 refers to people with MS who are able to walk without any aid and is based on measures of impairment in eight functional systems. EDSS steps 5.0 to 9.5 are defined by the impairment to walking.

For the research purposes participants were grouped into 3 categories based on the EDSS score:

- without neurological damage – absence of any or a presence of mild symptoms (EDSS 0-1,5),
- mild neurological damage (EDSS 2-3,5)- presence of certain symptoms that slightly affect the person's lifestyle and functioning
- moderate neurological deficit (EDSS 4-5,5) where there are no significant problems in terms of movement, but the symptoms of the disease cause problems in the daily functioning of the patient.

Results

Expanded Disability Status Scale (EDSS) score exploration

The severity of neurological deficits can affect other aspects of functioning. Participants with an EDSS score of 0-1.5 made up 20.4% of the sample and were categorized as not having a neurological deficit since they do not recognize it and

have no functional outbreaks. A mild neurological deficit (EDSS score 2-3.5) was the most common. In this category there was a percentage of 56.5 participants. Moderate neurological deficit in the examined population (EDSS score 4-5.5) was found in 23.1% of the participants.

PASAT score exploration

Results obtained by applying the serial addition test (PASAT) are presented in the table and show that the average score is 43.52 (SD = 19.84). Possible test score range is 0-60. Score 60 means the patients has preserved cognitive abilities, and score 0 indicates that the patients is not able to carry out the cognitive tasks provided by the instrument. Descriptive characteristics of the PASAT test can be found in Table 2.

Table 2. Descriptive characteristics of the PASAT test

	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
PASAT	108	0	60	43.52	19.84	-1.44	0.71

In the overall sample, 21 (19.4%) participant had a problem in cognitive functioning determined using the PASAT test, while 87 (80.6%) of the subjects did not have the same problem. When it comes to gender, 15 (21.4%) female participants had problems in cognitive functioning, while among men this number is 6 (15.8%) participants. Lower scores on the PASAT test which indicate problems in processing speed and attention span are more common in older subjects, in those with earlier symptom onset time as well as in cases where time elapsed since the diagnosis was longer. In order to determine the statistical significance, T test was performed. The results show that subjects with and without problems in cognitive functioning differ in terms of age and time elapsed since the diagnosis (Table 3). People with a detected problem in cognitive functioning measured by PASAT are older and the time elapsed since the establishment of MS diagnosis is longer. When compared to the time from the onset of symptoms, no significant differences were found between the individuals with and without problems in cognitive functioning.

Table 3. Differences in age, time elapsed since symptom onset and diagnosis in regard to categories of cognitive status

		PASAT – categories					
		N	Mean	SD	t	df	p
Age (in years)	Without problems in functioning	87	38.77	8.11	-2.91	106	0.00
	Present problems in functioning	21	44.38	7.10			
Time elapsed since the onset of symptoms	Without problems in functioning	87	11.78	6.89	-1.38	106	0.16
	Present problems in functioning	21	14.10	6.64			
Time elapsed since the diagnosis was established	Without problems in functioning	87	8.07	5.20	-2.82	106	0.00
	Present problems in functioning	21	11.52	4.21			

We have further investigated the differences in EDSS categories in relation to belonging to the category -with or -without problems in cognitive functioning on the PASAT test. The results show that there is no statistically significant difference ($\chi^2 = 5.636, p = 0.06$).

ARCS score exploration

For the purposes of this paper, we have extracted the subtest scores relevant to this study – Verbal fluency (Category, Activity and Letter), Verbal fluency – domain score and Language (Naming) (Table 4).

Table 4. Descriptive characteristics of the ARCS test results

Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
Total score	69.10	19.90	1	108	-0.24	0.35
Verbal fluency (Category)	14.05	3.49	4	23	0.04	0.02
Verbal fluency (Activity)	10.48	3.53	0	21	-0.20	1.33
Verbal fluency (Letter)	6.40	2.59	0	13	0.22	0.21
Verbal fluency – Domain score	31.07	8.17	7	51	-0.06	0.26
Language (Naming test)	8.47	1.55	3	10	-1.735	3.36

Regarding verbal fluency subtests, it is noted that the highest scores achieved belong to the subtest Category, and that the scores decrease from subtest to subtest, phonemic fluency (Letter) scores being the lowest. Regarding the Naming test, the average score is 8.47 and the maximum score is 10 points.

In further analysis, we showed the degree of deviation in persons with MS in relation to norms formed throughout the study conducted on the general population on a sample of 205 subjects. The group *No deviation* consists of all subjects with MS who have a regular finding, i.e. maximum achievements on the ARCS subcategories and deviations of less than -1SD when compared to the general population. A *Slight deviation* implies a deviation from the norm (for a general population of -1SD to -2SD), a *Moderate deviation* refers to results that from -2SD to -3SD, and the *Extreme deviation* includes deviations of -3SD and more (Table 5).

Table 5. A display of present cognitive impairments in ARCS subtests

		No deviation		S l i g h t deviation		M o d e r a t e deviation		E x t r e m e deviation	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Verbal	fluency	90	83.3	16	14.8	2	1.9	0	0
(Category)									
Verbal	fluency	96	88.9	9	8.3	3	2.8	0	0
(Activity)									
Verbal fluency (Letter)		94	87.0	12	11.1	2	1.9	0	0
Verbal fluency–Domain score		93	86.1	12	11.1	3	2.8	0	0
Language (Naming test)		97	89.8	5	4.6	3	2.8	3	2.8

Considering two instruments for assessing cognitive abilities were used, their interconnection was analysed. There is a significant positive correlation between the total score on the ARCS and PASAT test, which is $r = 0.24$, $p = 0.01$. These results show that if a person scores higher on one test, the same results should be expected on the other.

In further analysis, we examined the correlations of each ARCS subscale with the total score on the PASAT test (Table 6).

Table 6. Correlations between ARCS subtests and PASAT test scores

		PASAT
Verbal fluency (Category)	R	0.15
	P	0.12
Verbal fluency (Activity)	R	0.11
	P	0.22
Verbal fluency (Letter)	R	0.27**
	P	0.00
Verbal fluency – Domain score	R	0.18
	P	0.05
Language (Naming test)	R	-0.00
	P	0.94

The results show that the score on PASAT is significantly positively correlated to Verbal fluency (Letter) test scores.

In further data analysis we compared the ARCS and EDSS domain scores derived from this sample. There was a significant negative correlation between the total score on the EDSS test and the ARCS test ($p = -0.27$). There was also a negative correlation between Verbal fluency subtests and EDSS score. A higher score on EDSS, which indicates a poor neurological status, was followed by a lower score on the ARCS test, which means lower cognitive achievement in the examined cognitive domains. On the basis of the above mentioned, we can conclude that there is a positive correlation between the level of cognitive impairment and the degree of neurological deficits in patients with multiple sclerosis. That is, a greater neurological deficit is accompanied by the presence of cognitive deficits.

Discussion

Growing awareness and accumulating data regarding the cognitive impairment and its progression in MS patients has received an important place in neurological research in the past decade. Recent drug trials for relapsing remitting MS have shown some positive effects on neuropsychological measures (e.g. Riepl, et al., 2018). Thus, interest in defining a basic neuropsychological test battery and in deriving agreement as to the domains that need be tested in MS patients has become imperative.

Deficits in verbal fluency and language detrimentally affect many aspects of daily life, such as the ability to run a household, participate fully in society, and maintain employment - factors that can all affect the overall quality of life of the patient. Tests of verbal fluency typically require a subject to generate as many words as possible within a limited time from a particular semantic or letter category (e.g., “animals” or “words that start with F”). This task assesses language functions (vocabulary

size, naming), speed of response, mental organization, search strategies, short-term memory, and long term memory (Ruff, Light, Parker, & Levin, 1997). Verbal fluency is a popular neuropsychological test because it is easy and quick to administer, does not require writing or reading, and is sensitive to cognitive impairment from a variety of aetiologies.

In this paper, we examined the neuropsychological profile of patients with a diagnosis of clinically definite MS. The aim was to examine the possibility of using verbal fluency tests as a screening tool for cognitive impairment by comparing the results of verbal fluency subtests derived from ARCS to PASAT results upon a background of clinical features and EDSS score.

Based on the EDSS test results, 56.5% of the participants belonged to the group labelled as "mild neurological deficit", with a score of 2 - 3.5. The severity of neurological deficits can affect other aspects of functioning such as cognition which in turn affects the daily life of the patient. Test scores in this study indicate that there is no statistically significant difference when comparing the EDSS score to the PASAT scores obtained on this sample, which is consistent with the findings of Ruggieri et al. (Ruggieri, et al., 2003) on a sample of patients with an EDSS score ≤ 3.5 ; the rates of cognitive decline in both studies correlated with illness duration but were independent of EDSS score. Correspondingly, in the study of Deloire, Ruet, Hamel, Bonnet, & Brochet (Deloire, Ruet, Hamel, Bonnet, & Brochet, 2010) functional impairment was rated using the EDSS, whereas PASAT as a part of MSFC was included in the neuropsychological assessment, at baseline and five-year follow-up. The EDSS, but not the MSFC, deteriorated significantly over the 7 years, which could suggest a poor PASAT test reliability, consistent with our findings. Furthermore, a multivariate analysis showed correlations between the EDSS change over 5 and 7 years and two baseline tests evaluating information processing speed (IPS) and verbal memory. The deterioration of the EDSS after 7 years was significantly correlated with verbal memory testing at baseline. In conclusion, in this sample of MS patients early in the disease, the baseline IPS and verbal memory impairments predicted the EDSS score 5 and 7 years later. It is these findings that support the premise of neuropsychological testing, in particular verbal fluency tests, possibly being a sensitive and ecologically valid tool for detecting not only cognitive impairment and its progression, but the overall disability status of patients with MS.

For people with lifelong conditions such as MS, medical care system presents a breeding ground for stress and anxiety; these experiences emphasize the value of better diagnostic tools in terms of duration, efficacy and stress imposed by their administration. Neuropsychological assessment often requires utilization of extensive, time and energy-consuming test batteries. Patients report high level of stress and anxiety regarding the PASAT test administration (Cohen, Reingold, Polman, & Wolinsky, 2012). Alternatively, ARCS test has good validity and reliability, has a sound normative base and measures functioning in multiple cognitive domains while imposing minimal time demands upon the clinician as well as the patients. Fluency tests are reliable, quick to administer and even patients with quite severe deficits can understand the task requirements, all of which makes the verbal fluency testing a perfect candidate for a screening test on the presence

of cognitive impairments as well as the cognitive impairment rate progression over time.

Conclusion

Cognitive impairment is one of the most common features of MS that is present early in the course of the disease and has a significant negative impact on patients' quality of life as well as on their family and careers. Neuropsychological testing is the gold standard for assessing cognition but it is time consuming and many clinicians are deprived access to such assessments due to the lack of training and/or funding. The use of a rapid and easily applied screening test sensitive to cognitive impairment is a more practical approach as it can triage referral to neuropsychological testing and dictate further clinical assessment. Early detection of cognitive impairment could serve as a stepping stone towards realization of therapeutic interventions aimed at preventing further cognitive decline and reducing its impact on patients' lives. We believe verbal fluency tests could provide simple, cost-effective measures of cognitive dysfunction and should therefore be integrated into routine patient management.

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